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ORAL PRESENTATION

BIOMONITORING OF NON-OCCUPATIONAL ARSENIC EXPOSURE AMONG ADVANCED LUNG CANCER PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA

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Arsenic is wide spread global contaminant and Group 1 IARC carcinogen threatening human health due to intake through air, food and water. The newest findings indicate that exposure to low and moderate arsenic levels (<150 µg/L) are associated with elevated risk of developing or dying from lung cancer.

In this study a total of 190 lung IIIB/IV stage cancer patients of both genders (105 males and 85 females) from the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia were enrolled, 61 of whom were diagnosed with small-cell lung cancer, while 129 were diagnosed with non-small cell lung cancer (67 with lung adenocarcinoma and 62 with squamous cell lung cancer). Their first morning, urine sample was collected within 24h of hospitalization. Each sample was prepared using microwave digestion and tested for arsenic using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry analysis.

In 87.89% (167/190) samples arsenic was measured above the limit of quantification (LOQ) with no differences between genders as arsenic was above LOQ in 90.48% (95/105) samples of male patients and in 84.71% (72/85) samples of female patients. There were no statistical differences in the urinary arsenic values between genders ($p=0.323$) as the mean concentrations and standard deviations were 23.45 ± 39.89 µg/L for males vs. 18.05 ± 26.65 µg/L for female participants. The urinary arsenic concentrations were highest among patients with squamous cell lung cancer with 29.62 ± 48.04 µg/L and higher when compared to the levels measured among patients with small-cell lung cancer (15.80 ± 28.37 , $p=0.085$) and compared to those with lung adenocarcinoma (17.21 ± 20.70 , $p=0.066$), respectively with borderline significance in both cases. Since none of the participants was occupationally exposed to arsenic, environmental sources were observed as the main pathway of exposure.

Water remains one of the principal sources of exposure to arsenic. In the region of Vojvodina ground waters are endangered by arsenic with up to 750 µg/L while the concentration of arsenic in the drinking water is usually between 10 and 100 µg/L. Besides, the arsenic daily intake in Vojvodina in 2000 through food was estimated to be 60.9 ± 22.3 µg/day. There is an urgent need for regulatory measures to protect the general population from the cancer risks associated with arsenic exposure.

Keywords: arsenic, lung cancer, environmental pollution

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